

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Acceptance Note) for **TEBT-2024-0016**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Protocol for a systematic evidence map of the state-of-the-art assessment of risks related to chemical contamination from abandoned mine lands
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0016
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	4 (3 peer-reviewers + 1 editor)
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study) ▾
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246186
Evaluation Round	Round 4 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	2 Nov 2025
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

The authors have submitted a protocol for an evidence map that aims to describe the “state of the art” (standards in contemporary practice) in abandoned mine land (AML) risk assessment. In my opinion, this is an interesting objective for an evidence map: summarising the contemporary

state of methods in a domain seems like a very useful application of the method that I don't recall seeing before.

In the first round of review, the reviewers commented favourably on the protocol but also recommended revisions to improve the conciseness and structure of the protocol, clarify the objectives, provide more detail around data abstraction and coding methods, and either improve the scientific justification for the specific approach being taken or modify the planned approach.

In the second round of review, the reviewers acknowledged the significant efforts made by the authors to improve their protocol, finding all substantive issues to have been satisfactorily addressed. Only minor further revisions were recommended, mainly in relation to improving the clarity and wording of some parts of the manuscript. The handling editor reviewed the final revisions and determined that the authors had responded satisfactorily to the recommended changes, and therefore accepted the manuscript for publication.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 2 rounds of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

In the editor's opinion, this protocol is a Category 1 preregistration (the authors are likely to have seen data they will be collecting and analysing in their review; however, as an exploratory mapping exercise, this seems unlikely to bias the study's findings). According to our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at [insert hyperlinked DOI].
